

REACHABILITY DEGREE SUM ENERGY OF GRAPH

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Abstract

Let G be a simple connected graph with p vertices and q edges. In this paper, we introduce the reachability degree sum energy of a graph and obtained reachability degree sum energy of some graphs. Also, we establish the upper and lower bound for this new energy.

Keywords: Energy, Reachability Matrix, Degree Sum Matrix, Reachability Degree Sum Matrix, Reachability Degree Sum Eigen Values.

1. INTRODUCTION

The energy of a simple graph was introduced by Ivan Gutman in 1978[8, 9]. The energy of a graph G , denoted by $E(G)$, is defined to be the sum of the absolute value of the eigenvalues of its adjacency matrix (i.e) $E(G) = \sum_{i=1}^p |\lambda_i|$. There are many energies based on Distance matrix [3, 7, 11], Laplacian matrix [2], Harary matrix [5] etc.

Let G be a simple connected graph with p vertices and q edges. The reachability matrix $\mathbb{R}(G) = (r_{ij})$ is a square matrix of order p with $r_{ij} = 1$ if t_j is reachable from t_i and 0 otherwise [1]. The Characteristic polynomial of a $\mathbb{R}(G)$ is $\phi(G, \beta) = \det(\mathbb{R}(G) - \beta I)$, where I is the identity matrix. the roots of the equation $\phi(G, \beta) = 0$ is called the Eigen values of the reachability matrix. Since $\mathbb{R}(G)$ is real and symmetric, its eigenvalues are real numbers and denoted by $\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_p$, we label them in non- increasing order $\beta_1 \geq \beta_2 \geq \beta_3 \geq \dots \geq \beta_p$. The collection of \mathbb{R} - eigenvalues is called spectrum of a graph G [4, 10].

Ramane H S et.al introduced the degree sum matrix in 2013 [6, 12, 13]. Let G be a simple connected graph with p vertices and q edges. The degree sum matrix of a graph G is denoted as $DS(G)$ is defined as $DSM(G) = [d_{ij}]$ where $d_{ij} = d_i + d_j$ when $i \neq j$ and 0 otherwise. The Characteristic polynomial of $DSM(G)$ is $\phi(G, \alpha) = \det(DSM(G) - \alpha I)$, where I is the identity matrix. The roots of the equation $\phi(G, \alpha) = 0$ is called the eigen values of the degree sum matrix. Since $DSM(G)$ is real and symmetric, its eigenvalues are real numbers and denoted by $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_p$, we label them in non-increasing order $\alpha_1 \geq \alpha_2 \geq \alpha_3 \geq \dots \geq \alpha_p$. Motivated by above studies, In this paper, we will introduce a new energy and index of the graph based on reachability degree sum matrix and also obtain lower and upper bounds for this new energy and new index of the graph G .

2. REACHABILITY DEGREE SUM MATRIX OF GRAPH

In this section, we introduce a new matrix called reachability degree sum matrix and also, we obtain lemma necessary to find its bounds.

Definition 2.1:

Let G be a simple connected graph with p vertices and q edges. Reachability degree sum matrix, denoted by $\mathbb{R}_{DS}M(G)$, defined by

$$\mathbb{R}_{DS}M(G) = (\gamma_{ij}) = \begin{cases} r_{ij} + d_i + d_j, & t_j \text{ is reachable from } t_i \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Where d_i = degree of the vertex t_i . The Characteristic polynomial of a $\mathbb{R}_{DS}M(G)$ is $\phi(G, \delta) = \det(\mathbb{R}_{DS}M(G) - \delta I)$, where I is the identity matrix. the roots of the equation $\phi(G, \delta) = 0$ is called the Eigen values of the reachability degree sum matrix. Since $\mathbb{R}_{DS}M(G)$ is real and symmetric, its eigenvalues are real numbers and denoted by $\delta_1, \delta_2, \dots, \delta_p$, we label them in non- increasing order $\delta_1 \geq \delta_2 \geq \delta_3 \geq \dots \geq \delta_p$. The collection of \mathbb{R}_{DS} - eigenvalues is called spectrum of a graph G . The sum of the absolute values of the eigenvalues of $\mathbb{R}_{DS}M(G)$ is known as reachability degree sum energy of a graph G , denoted by $\mathbb{R}_{DS}E(G)$, is defined by $\mathbb{R}_{DS}E(G) = \sum_{i=1}^p |\delta_i|$.

Lemma 2.1:

Let G be a connected graph of order p and let $\delta_1, \delta_2, \dots, \delta_p$ be eigenvalues of $\mathbb{R}_{DS}M(G)$. Then

$$\sum_{i=1}^p \delta_i = 0 \quad \& \quad \sum_{i=1}^p \delta_i^2 = 2 \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq p} (r_{ij} + d_i + d_j)^2$$

Proof:

We know that $\sum_{i=1}^p \delta_i$ is equal to the trace of a matrix and also the reachability degree sum matrix of a graph is defined as

$$\mathbb{R}_{DS}(G) = (\gamma_{ij}) \text{ where } \gamma_{ij} = r_{ij} + d_i + d_j \text{ when } i \neq j \text{ and } 0 \text{ otherwise.}$$

$$\text{Now, } \sum_{i=1}^p \delta_i = \text{trace}(\mathbb{R}_{DS}(G)) = \sum_{i=j=1}^p \gamma_{ij} = 0.$$

Moreover, for $i = 1, 2, \dots, p$, the (i, i) th entry of $(\mathbb{R}_{DS}(G))^2$ is equal to $\sum_{j=1}^p (\gamma_{ij})(\gamma_{ji}) = \sum_{i=1}^p (\gamma_{ij})^2$

$$\sum_{i=1}^p \gamma_i^2 = \text{trace}(\mathbb{R}_{DS}(G))^2 = \sum_{i=1}^p \sum_{j=1}^p (\gamma_{ij})^2 = 2 \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq p} (r_{ij} + d_i + d_j)^2.$$

Hence the result.

3. BOUNDS FOR REACHABILITY DEGREE SUM ENERGY OF GRAPH

In this section, we obtain bounds for reachability degree sum energy of a graph G .

Theorem 3.1:

If G be a (p, q) connected graph, then

$$\sqrt{2 \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq p} (r_{ij} + d_i + d_j)^2} \leq \mathbb{R}_{DS}E(G) \leq \sqrt{2p \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq p} (r_{ij} + d_i + d_j)^2}.$$

Proof:

By Cauchy-Schwartz inequality,

$$\left(\sum_{i=1}^p a_i b_i \right)^2 \leq \left(\sum_{i=1}^p a_i^2 \right) \left(\sum_{i=1}^p b_i^2 \right)$$

Consider, $a_i = 1$ and $b_i = |\delta_i|$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\sum_{i=1}^p |\delta_i| \right)^2 &\leq p \left(\sum_{i=1}^p \delta_i^2 \right) \\ \mathbb{R}_{DS}E(G)^2 &\leq 2p \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq p} (r_{ij} + d_i + d_j)^2 \\ \mathbb{R}_{DS}E(G) &\leq \sqrt{2p \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq p} (r_{ij} + d_i + d_j)^2}. \end{aligned}$$

Which gives the required upper bound for $\mathbb{R}_{DS}E(G)$.

We can easily obtain the inequality,

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathbb{R}_{DS}E(G))^2 &= \left(\sum_{i=1}^p |\delta_i| \right)^2 \geq \sum_{i=1}^p |\delta_i|^2 = 2 \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq p} (r_{ij} + d_i + d_j)^2 \\ \mathbb{R}_{DS}E(G) &\geq \sqrt{2 \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq p} (r_{ij} + d_i + d_j)^2}. \end{aligned}$$

Which gives the required lower bound for $\mathbb{R}_{DS}E(G)$.

Hence the result.

Theorem 3.2:

Let G be a (p, q) connected graph and let Δ be the absolute value of the determinant of the reachability degree sum matrix $\mathbb{R}_{DS}M(G)$ of a graph then

$$\sqrt{2 \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq p} (r_{ij} + d_i + d_j)^2 + p(p-1)\Delta^{\frac{2}{p}}} \leq \mathbb{R}_{DS}E(G) \leq \sqrt{2p \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq p} (r_{ij} + d_i + d_j)^2}.$$

Proof:

By theorem 3.1, we have upper bound for $\mathbb{R}_{DS}E(G)$.

Now, we show that the lower bound for $\mathbb{R}_{DS}E(G)$ then this will finish the proof.

By definition of reachability degree sum energy,

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathbb{R}_{DS}E(G))^2 &= \left(\sum_{i=1}^p |\delta_i| \right)^2 = \sum_{i=1}^p |\delta_i|^2 + 2 \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq p} |\delta_i| |\delta_j| \\ &= 2 \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq p} (r_{ij} + d_i + d_j)^2 + \sum_{i \neq j} |\delta_i| |\delta_j| \end{aligned}$$

From Arithmetic – Geometric Mean Inequality, we have,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{p(p-1)} \sum_{i \neq j} |\delta_i| |\delta_j| &\geq \left(\prod_{i \neq j} |\delta_i| |\delta_j| \right)^{\frac{1}{p(p-1)}} \\ &= \left(\prod_{i=1}^p |\delta_i|^{2(p-1)} \right)^{\frac{1}{p(p-1)}} = \Delta^{\frac{2}{p}} \\ \sum_{i \neq j} |\delta_i| |\delta_j| &\geq \Delta^{\frac{2}{p}} \end{aligned}$$

Which gives

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathbb{R}_{DS}E(G))^2 &\geq 2 \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq p} (r_{ij} + d_i + d_j)^2 + p(p-1)\Delta^{\frac{2}{p}} \\ \mathbb{R}_{DS}E(G) &\geq \sqrt{2 \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq p} (r_{ij} + d_i + d_j)^2 + p(p-1)\Delta^{\frac{2}{p}}}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence the result.

4. REACHABILITY DEGREE SUM ENERGY OF SOME GRAPHS

In this section, we obtain reachability degree sum energy for some graphs.

Theorem 4.1:

Reachability degree sum energy of path graph P_p is $\mathbb{R}_{DS}E(P_p) = 2(5p - 12) \forall p \geq 4$.

Proof:

Consider a path graph P_p with p vertices. The reachability degree sum matrix $\mathbb{R}_{DS}M(P_p)$ is

$$\mathbb{R}_{DS}M(P_p) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 4 & 4 & \cdots & 4 & 3 \\ 4 & 0 & 5 & \cdots & 5 & 4 \\ 4 & 5 & 0 & \cdots & 5 & 4 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 4 & 5 & 5 & \cdots & 0 & 4 \\ 3 & 4 & 4 & \cdots & 4 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Let us find the spectrum of $\mathbb{R}_{DS}M(P_p)$ using the relation,

$$\phi(P_p, \delta) = \det(\mathbb{R}_{DS}M(P_p) - \delta I), \text{ where } I \text{ is the identity matrix.}$$

$$\phi(P_p, \beta) = \begin{vmatrix} -\delta & 4 & 4 & \cdots & 4 & 3 \\ 4 & -\delta & 5 & \cdots & 5 & 4 \\ 4 & 5 & -\delta & \cdots & 5 & 4 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 4 & 5 & 5 & \cdots & -\delta & 4 \\ 3 & 4 & 4 & \cdots & 4 & -\delta \end{vmatrix} = 0$$

Hence, the spectrum of $\mathbb{R}_{DS}M(P_p)$ is

$$\left(\begin{matrix} -3 & -5 & \frac{5p-12+\sqrt{25p^2-52p+68}}{2} \\ 1 & p-3 & 1 \end{matrix} \right).$$

The reachability energy $\mathbb{R}_{DS}E(P_p)$ can be determined as follows: $\mathbb{R}_{DS}E(P_p) = \sum_{i=1}^p |\delta_i|$

$$= (|-3| \times 1) + (|-5| \times (p-3)) + \left(\left| \frac{5p-12+\sqrt{25p^2-52p+68}}{2} \right| \times 1 \right) + \left(\left| \frac{5p-12-\sqrt{25p^2-52p+68}}{2} \right| \times 1 \right)$$

$$= 3 + 5p - 15 + 5p - 12 = 10p - 24 = 2(5p - 12).$$

$$\mathbb{R}_{DS}E(P_p) = 2(5p - 12).$$

This completes the proof.

Example 4.1:

Bounds of Reachability degree sum energy of path graph is given in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1. Bounds of Reachability Degree Sum Energy of Path Graph

Vertices p	$\sqrt{2 \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq p} (r_{ij} + d_i + d_j)^2}$	$\mathbb{R}_{DS}E(P_p)$	$\sqrt{2p \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq p} (r_{ij} + d_i + d_j)^2}$
4	14	16	28
5	18.973	26	42.426
6	23.958	36	58.685
\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots
p	$\sqrt{25p^2 - 61p + 40}$	$2(5p - 12)$	$\sqrt{p(25p^2 - 61p + 40)}$

Theorem 4.2:

Reachability degree sum energy of Cycle graph C_p is $\mathbb{R}_{DS}E(C_p) = 10(p - 1) \forall p \geq 3$.

Proof:

Consider a cycle graph C_p with p vertices. The reachability degree sum matrix $\mathbb{R}_{DS}M(C_p)$ is

$$\mathbb{R}_{DS}M(C_p) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 5 & 5 & \dots & 5 & 5 \\ 5 & 0 & 5 & \dots & 5 & 5 \\ 5 & 5 & 0 & \dots & 5 & 5 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 5 & 5 & 5 & \dots & 0 & 5 \\ 5 & 5 & 5 & \dots & 5 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Let us find the spectrum of $\mathbb{R}_{DS}M(C_p)$ using the relation,

$$\phi(C_p, \delta) = \det(\mathbb{R}_{DS}M(C_p) - \delta I), \text{ where } I \text{ is the identity matrix.}$$

$$\phi(C_p, \beta) = \begin{vmatrix} -\delta & 5 & 5 & \dots & 5 & 5 \\ 5 & -\delta & 5 & \dots & 5 & 5 \\ 5 & 5 & -\delta & \dots & 5 & 5 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 5 & 5 & 5 & \dots & -\delta & 5 \\ 5 & 5 & 5 & \dots & 5 & -\delta \end{vmatrix} = 0$$

Hence, the spectrum of $\mathbb{R}_{DS}M(C_p)$ is

$$\begin{pmatrix} 5(p - 1) & -5 \\ 1 & p - 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

The reachability energy $\mathbb{R}_{DS}E(C_p)$ can be determined as follows: $\mathbb{R}_{DS}E(C_p) = \sum_{i=1}^p |\delta_i|$

$$\mathbb{R}_{DS}E(C_p) = (|5(p - 1)| \times 1) + (|-5| \times (p - 1)) = 10p - 10 = 10(p - 1).$$

$$\mathbb{R}_{DS}E(C_p) = 10(p - 1).$$

This completes the proof.

Example 4.2:

Bounds of Reachability degree sum energy of cycle graph is given in Table 4.2.

Table 4.2. Bounds of Reachability Degree Sum Energy of Cycle Graph

Vertices p	$\sqrt{2 \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq p} (r_{ij} + d_i + d_j)^2}$	$\mathbb{R}_{DS}E(C_p)$	$\sqrt{2p \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq p} (r_{ij} + d_i + d_j)^2}$
3	12.247	20	21.213
4	17.320	30	34.641
5	22/360	40	50
\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots
p	$5\sqrt{p(p-1)}$	$10(p-1)$	$5p\sqrt{p-1}$

Theorem 4.3:

Reachability degree sum energy of complete graph K_p is $\mathbb{R}_{DS}E(K_p) = 2(2p^2 - 3p + 1)$
 $\forall p \geq 3$.

Proof:

Consider a complete graph K_p with p vertices. The reachability degree sum matrix $\mathbb{R}_{DS}M(K_p)$ is

$$\mathbb{R}_{DS}M(K_p) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 2p-1 & 2p-1 & \cdots & 2p-1 & 2p-1 \\ 2p-1 & 0 & 2p-1 & \cdots & 2p-1 & 2p-1 \\ 2p-1 & 2p-1 & 0 & \cdots & 2p-1 & 2p-1 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 2p-1 & 2p-1 & 2p-1 & \cdots & 0 & 2p-1 \\ 2p-1 & 2p-1 & 2p-1 & \cdots & 2p-1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Let us find the spectrum of $\mathbb{R}_{DS}M(K_p)$ using the relation,

$$\phi(K_p, \delta) = \det(\mathbb{R}_{DS}M(K_p) - \delta I), \text{ where } I \text{ is the identity matrix.}$$

$$\phi(K_p, \beta) = \begin{vmatrix} -\delta & 2p-1 & 2p-1 & \cdots & 2p-1 & 2p-1 \\ 2p-1 & -\delta & 2p-1 & \cdots & 2p-1 & 2p-1 \\ 2p-1 & 2p-1 & -\delta & \cdots & 2p-1 & 2p-1 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 2p-1 & 2p-1 & 2p-1 & \cdots & -\delta & 2p-1 \\ 2p-1 & 2p-1 & 2p-1 & \cdots & 2p-1 & -\delta \end{vmatrix} = 0$$

Hence, the spectrum of $\mathbb{R}_{DS}M(K_p)$ is

$$\begin{pmatrix} 2p^2 - 3p + 1 & -(2p-1) \\ 1 & p-1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

The reachability energy $\mathbb{R}_{DS}E(K_p)$ can be determined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{R}_{DS}E(K_p) &= \sum_{i=1}^p |\delta_i| = (|2p^2 - 3p + 1| \times 1) + (|-(2p - 1)| \times (p - 1)) \\ &= 2p^2 - 3p + 1 + 2p^2 - p - 2p + 1 = 4p^2 - 6p + 2 = 2(2p^2 - 3p + 1). \\ \mathbb{R}_{DS}E(K_p) &= 2(2p^2 - 3p + 1). \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof.

Example 4.3:

Bounds of Reachability degree sum energy of complete graph is given in Table 4.3.

Table 4.3. Bounds of Reachability Degree Sum Energy of Complete Graph

Vertices p	$\sqrt{2 \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq p} (r_{ij} + d_i + d_j)^2}$	$\mathbb{R}_{DS}E(K_p)$	$\sqrt{2p \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq p} (r_{ij} + d_i + d_j)^2}$
3	12.247	20	21.213
4	24.248	42	48.490
5	40.249	72	90
\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots
p	$\sqrt{p(4p^3 - 8p^2 + 5p - 1)}$	$2(2p^2 - 3p + 1)$	$\sqrt{p^2(4p^3 - 8p^2 + 5p - 1)}$

Theorem 4.4:

Reachability degree sum energy of wheel graph W_p is $\mathbb{R}_{DS}E(W_p) = 14(p - 1) \forall p \geq 4$.

Proof:

Consider a wheel graph W_p with p vertices. The reachability degree sum matrix $\mathbb{R}_{DS}M(W_p)$ is

$$\mathbb{R}_{DS}M(W_p) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 7 & 7 & \cdots & 7 & p+4 \\ 7 & 0 & 7 & \cdots & 7 & p+4 \\ 7 & 7 & 0 & \cdots & 7 & p+4 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 7 & 7 & 7 & \cdots & 0 & p+4 \\ p+4 & p+4 & p+4 & \cdots & p+4 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Let us find the spectrum of $\mathbb{R}_{DS}M(W_p)$ using the relation,

$$\phi(W_p, \delta) = \det(\mathbb{R}_{DS}M(W_p) - \delta I), \text{ where } I \text{ is the identity matrix.}$$

$$\phi(W_p, \beta) = \begin{vmatrix} -\delta & 7 & 7 & \cdots & 7 & p+4 \\ 7 & -\delta & 7 & \cdots & 7 & p+4 \\ 7 & 7 & -\delta & \cdots & 7 & p+4 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 7 & 7 & 7 & \cdots & -\delta & p+4 \\ p+4 & p+4 & p+4 & \cdots & p+4 & -\delta \end{vmatrix} = 0$$

Hence, the spectrum of $\mathbb{R}_{DS}M(W_p)$ is

$$\begin{pmatrix} -7 & \frac{7(p-1) \pm \sqrt{4p^3 + 81p^2 - 34p + 48}}{2} \\ p-1 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

The reachability energy $\mathbb{R}_{DS}E(W_p)$ can be determined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{R}_{DS}E(W_p) &= \sum_{i=1}^p |\delta_i| \\ &= (|-7| \times (p-1)) + \left(\left| \frac{7(p-1) + \sqrt{4p^3 + 81p^2 - 34p + 48}}{2} \right| \times 1 \right) + \left(\left| \frac{7(p-1) - \sqrt{4p^3 + 81p^2 - 34p + 48}}{2} \right| \times 1 \right) \\ &= 7(p-1) + 7(p-1) = 14(p-1). \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbb{R}_{DS}E(C_p) = 14(p-1).$$

This completes the proof.

Example 4.4:

Bounds of Reachability degree sum energy of wheel graph is given in Table 4.4.

Table 4.4. Bounds of Reachability Degree Sum Energy of Wheel Graph

Vertices p	$\sqrt{2 \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq p} (r_{ij} + d_i + d_j)^2}$	$\mathbb{R}_{DS}E(W_p)$	$\sqrt{2p \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq p} (r_{ij} + d_i + d_j)^2}$
4	33.166	42	66.332
5	42.308	56	94.604
6	51.672	70	126.570
\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots
p	$\sqrt{p(2p^2 + 65p - 17)}$	$14(p-1)$	$p\sqrt{2p^2 + 65p - 17}$

CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have introduced and obtained the reachability degree sum energy of graph of order p . Also, we have found its bounds of this energy of graph of order p . Further, we obtained reachability degree sum energy of some graphs such as path graph, cycle graph, complete graph and wheel graph.

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